

Photolytic Separation of Uranium from Thorium, Zirconium, and Manganese

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Separation of uranium from thorium, zirconium, and manganese has been effected by photochemical process using their sulphate solution. Role of alcohol on the recovery of uranium has been investigated.

The photolytic separation of uranium from vanadium using sulphate solutions, reported earlier (Mishra *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 753), stipulated the pH range of 2.1 to 2.3 and the exposure period of fifteen hours as the necessary optimum conditions. The present communication deals with the separation of uranium from thorium, zirconium, and manganese by the same method, maintaining the same pH range and the period of exposure. The effect of variation of the alcoholic composition on the purity and recovery of the product has been investigated in each case.

EXPERIMENTAL

Uranium nitrate, zirconium nitrate, and manganese sulphate used were of E. Merck quality. Thorium nitrate was of B. D. H. AnalaR quality. The preparation of the solutions for photolysis and the analysis of the products obtained after exposure were carried out as reported previously (Singh *et al.*, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1959, 50A, 129).

Table I shows that in case of separation of uranium from thorium, single-stage photolysis yields uranium of 96% purity. When photolysis was carried out for the second time, the purity of uranium recovered went up to 99.8%, as can be seen from Table II. It is evident that 20 to 30% alcoholic composition is suitable for photolysis. When separation is made from zirconium and manganese, single-stage photolysis yields uranium of 99.8% purity, though increase of alcoholic composition has a marked effect so far as recovery of uranium from manganese is concerned. The analytical data for the recovery of uranium from zirconium and manganese have been recorded in Tables III and IV respectively.

TABLE I
Separation of uranium from thorium.

Composition of the mixture as oxides.		%Alcohol.	Analysis of precipitate.		%Purity.	%Recovery.
U ₃ O ₈ .	ThO ₂ .		Total oxide by ignition.	U ₃ O ₈ by Cd reductor.		
417.2 mg.	85.4 mg.	20	376.0 mg.	363.9 mg.	96.8	87.2
417.2	85.4	30	397.5	383.6	96.5	92.0
417.2	85.4	40	404.5	375.8	92.9	80.1
417.2	85.4	50	411.5	317.9	90.4	89.1

TABLE II

Composition of the mixture as oxides.		Percentage of alcohol.		Analysis of precipitate.		%Purity.	%Recovery.
U ₃ O ₈ .	ThO ₂ .	1st photolysis.	2nd photolysis.	Total oxide by ignition	U ₃ O ₈ by Cd reductor.		
417.2 mg.	85.4 mg.	20	20	373.4 mg.	372.7 mg.	99.8	89.3
417.2	85.4	20	50	375.3	372.2	99.1	89.2

TABLE III

Separation of uranium from zirconium.

Composition of the mixture as oxides.		%Alcohol.	Analysis of precipitate.		%Purity.	%Recovery.
U ₃ O ₈ .	ZrO ₂ .		Total oxide by ignition.	U ₃ O ₈ by Cd reductor.		
417.2 mg.	110.3 mg.	20	370.3 mg.	369.2 mg.	99.7	88.5
417.2	110.3	30	384.6	383.8	99.8	92.0
417.2	110.3	40	395.6	394.8	99.8	94.5
417.2	110.3	50	397.4	396.7	99.8	95.1

TABLE IV

Separation of uranium from manganese.

Composition of the mixture as oxides.		%Alcohol.	Analysis of precipitate.		%Purity.	%Recovery.
U ₃ O ₈ .	MnO ₂ .		Total oxide by ignition.	U ₃ O ₈ by Cd reductor.		
417.2 mg.	103.9 mg.	20	293.9 mg.	293.3 mg.	99.8	70.3
417.2	103.9	30	315.1	314.6	99.8	75.4
417.2	103.9	40	370.2	369.2	99.7	88.5
417.2	103.9	50	373.0	371.9	99.7	89.1